

NUMERICAL EVALUATION OF THERMAL WARPAGE ON FLIP CHIP PACKAGE WITH RESPECT TO LAYER RESIDUAL RATE

W. Song¹, Y. Byun², T. Ku¹, J. Kim², M. Kim³, H. Kang³, B. Kang^{2*}

¹ Industrial Liaison Innovation Center, Pusan National University, Busan, S. Korea, ² Dept. of Aerospace Eng., Pusan National University, Busan, S. Korea, ³ BGA R&D Group, Samsung Electro-Mechanics Co., Ltd., Chungcheongnamdo, S. Korea

* Corresponding author (H**bskang@pusan.ac.kr**H)

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1 Introduction

The reliability problems of flip chip (FC) packages subjected to temperature change during the packaging process mainly occur due to mismatches in the coefficients of thermal expansion [1]. FC package is generally consisted with main chip (Silicon), underfill and bare printed circuit board (PCB), as shown in Fig. 1. Resin molding compounds like underfill and glass fiber reinforced epoxy composites (GFRC) used in FC package strongly exhibit temperature-dependent material properties [2, 3]. In this study, the thermal warpage of FC package is evaluated using finite element analysis (FEA). The thermal warpage of FC package was simulated and compared with respect to the variation of Cu and SR film residual rates in bare

PCB, in case that the material selection and thickness of each layer are under the restriction without change. It is noted that the coplanarity of FC package can be enhanced with about 30% as only adjusting the residual rates of Cu and SR film in bare PCB.

2 Finite Element Analysis

2.1 Finite Element Model

Numerical simulation is performed for the whole body of FC package with main chip, underfill and bare PCB. Finite element model of FC package is shown in Fig. 2. Bare PCB is constructed by SR film, GFRC prepreg and Cu layers. Main chip and underfill area are modeled by solid element and bare PCB is modeled by layered shell element. The nodes in the sharing region between underfill and bare PCB are merged in the finite element model. Solder bumps in the underfill region are ignored in this analysis due to the relatively weak mechanical characteristics of the bump. The residual rates on Cu

Fig.1. Schematic diagram of flip chip package.

Table 1. The given condition on Cu & SR residual rate in bare printed circuit board.

Layer	Residual Rate [%]
Upper SR	89.2
Cu	56.6
Prepreg	-
Cu	60.2
Prepreg	-
Cu	47.0
Prepreg	-
Cu	52.1
Lower SR	76.6

Fig.2. Finite element model and layer construction of bare printed circuit board.

(a) Young's moduli of GFRC and underfill

(b) Stress-strain relationship of Cu

Fig.3. Mechanical properties of layer materials in flip chip package.

and SR layer were given in Table. 1. In this study, the residual rates are main parameters to evaluate the thermal coplanarity of FC package.

2.2 Material Properties

Mechanical properties of underfill and GFRC Prepreg are shown in Fig. 3, which are temperature dependent and measured by DMA Q800 of TA instruments. Thermal properties of underfill, GFRC Prepreg, SR film and Cu are also shown in Fig. 4, which are also temperature dependent and measured by TMA 4000SA of Material Analysis & Characterization. The mechanical and thermal properties of GFRC were tested in orthogonal directions due to the orthogonal material characteristics of GFRC. Fig. 3 shows the stress-strain relation of Cu. Silicon is considered as an isotropic, perfectly-elastic and temperature-independent material with E: 169GPa, CTE: 3.0E-6.

2.3 Simulation Conditions

(a) CTEs of underfill and SR film

(b) CTEs of GFRC and Cu

Fig.4. Thermal properties of layer materials in flip chip package.

Fig.5. Thermal environment in the package process of FC package.

Thermal environment in the packaging process of FC package is shown in Fig. 5. In this simulation, the temperature change is assigned in the whole finite element models with room temperature (25°C) after peak value (240°C). To evaluate the thermal

Table 2. Parametric study conditions on Cu & SR residual rates.

Layer	Variation of Cu & SR Residual Rate [%]								
	No.1	No.2	No.3	No.4	No.5	No.6	No.7	No.8	No.9
U_SR	↓1	↓5	↓10	-	-	-	↓1	↓5	↓10
Cu	↑1	↑5	↑10	-	-	-	↑1	↑5	↑10
PPG	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
Cu	↑1	↑5	↑10	-	-	-	↑1	↑5	↑10
PPG	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
Cu	-	-	-	↓1	↓5	↓10	↓1	↓5	↓10
PPG	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
Cu	-	-	-	↓1	↓5	↓10	↓1	↓5	↓10
L_SR	-	-	-	↑1	↑5	↑10	↑1	↑5	↑10

Fig.6. Thermal warpage and deforming configuration of the given FC package model.

Fig.7. Thermal warpage comparison

warping of FC package, the Cu and SR film residual rates in bare PCB were changed. The variations of Cu and SR film residual rates in bare PCB for each model (No.1 ~ 9) are shown in Table 2. Through the result of the FEA for the given residual rate model in Fig. 6., it is noted that bare PCB was deformed as the convex configuration and main chip was deformed as the concave configuration due to the coefficient of thermal expansion mismatch.

3 Results and Discussions

The thermal warpage of FC package was evaluated

Fig.8. Thermal warpage configurations with respect to variation of Cu & SR residual rate.

with the variation conditions of the residual rates on Cu and SR film as shown in Table 2, which conditions were determined from the primitive FEA result for the given model. The results of the FEA of the model No.1 to 9 are shown in Fig. 7 and 8. As you can see Fig. 7, the adjustment of the residual rates of Cu and SR film in bare PCB can improve the coplanarity of FC package with about 30% for the temperature change.

It is concluded that the proposed concept of the adjustment of residual rates on Cu and SR film can play a feasible role to reduce the thermal warpage in the design stage of FC package as the design guideline in the semiconductor industry.

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